

Direct and derivative spectrophotometric determination of cobalt(II) with 2,4-dihydroxybenzaldehyde isonicotinoyl hydrazone

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Abstract : A simple and sensitive spectrophotometric method is developed for the determination of cobalt in aqueous medium. The metal ion forms a brown coloured partially soluble complex with 2,4-dihydroxybenzaldehyde isonicotinoyl hydrazone (2,4-DHBINH) in the pH range 2–10. However, the complex is found to be soluble in 25% aqueous DMF. The complex shows an absorbance maximum at 405 nm in the pH range 5–6. Beer's law is obeyed in the range 0.062–1.5 µg/ml at pH 5.5. The molar absorptivity and the Sandell's sensitivity of the method are $3.20 \pm 0.03 \times 10^4 \text{ L mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and 0.0074 µg/cm^2 respectively. The composition of the complex is 1 : 1. A method for the determination of cobalt by first order derivative spectrophotometry is also proposed. The method is applied for the determination of cobalt in alloy steel samples.

Keywords : Substituted hydrazone, cobalt(II), derivative spectrophotometry.

2-Hydroxybenzaldehyde isonicotinoyl hydrazone has been used for the spectrophotometric determination of cobalt(II)¹. In our laboratory, 2,4-dihydroxybenzaldehyde isonicotinoyl hydrazone (2,4-DHBINH) has been synthesized and applied as a spectrophotometric reagent for the determination of titanium(IV), molybdenum(VI) and thorium(IV)².

Derivative spectrophotometry is a very useful approach for determining the concentration of simple components in mixtures with overlapping spectra as it eliminates much of the interference³. 2,4-DHBINH reacts with cobalt(II) in aqueous DMF forming a highly sensitive and stable brown coloured complex. This has been systematically studied both by direct and first derivative spectrophotometrically and the results obtained are presented in this paper.

Experimental

Shimadzu UV-visible spectrophotometer model UV-160A and ELICO pH meter model LI 120 were employed for absorbance and pH measurements respectively. Suitable settings for first order derivative are as follows : spectral band width 2 nm; wavelength readability 0.1 nm increment, scan speed fast (nearly 2400 nm min^{-1}); wavelength accuracy $\pm 0.5 \text{ nm}$ with automatic wavelength correction and with 9 degrees of freedom.

2,4-Dihydroxybenzaldehyde isonicotinoyl hydrazone : The reagent was prepared by condensing 2,4-

dihydroxybenzaldehyde and isonicotinic acid hydrazide in methanol using a general procedure (m.p. $290 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$)⁴. The structure of the reagent is as follows

A freshly prepared solution in dimethylformamide is used in the studies.

A 0.1–0.5 g of the alloy was dissolved in a mixture of 2 ml HCl and 10 ml HNO₃. The resulting solution was evaporated to a small volume. To this 5 ml of 1 : 1 (H₂O : H₂SO₄) mixture was added and evaporated to dryness. The residue was dissolved in 15 ml of distilled water and filtered through Whatman Filter paper No. 41. The filtrate is collected in a 100 ml volumetric flask and made up to the mark with distilled water.

Cobalt solution (0.01 M) : Prepared by dissolving the 0.2910 g of Co(NO₃)₂·6H₂O (A.R., B.D.H.) in 100 ml distilled water. The resulting cobalt(II) solution was standardized gravimetrically⁵.

For the preparation of buffer solutions, 1 M HCl and 1 M sodium acetate (pH 1.0 to 8.0), 0.2 M acetic acid and 0.2 M sodium acetate (pH 3.2 to 7.0) were used.

Direct spectrophotometry : In each set of different 10 ml standard flasks, 5 ml of buffer solution (pH 5.5), 3 ml of dimethylformamide (DMF) and 0.5 ml of 2,4-DHBINH ($6.0 \times 10^{-3} M$) were taken. Various amounts of cobalt(II) were added to these flasks and made up to the mark with distilled water. The absorbance was measured at 405 nm against the reagent blank. The calibration curve was prepared by plotting the absorbance against the amount of cobalt.

First order derivative spectrophotometry : For the above solutions, first order derivative spectra were recorded (slit width of 1 nm, with degrees of freedom 9) in the wavelength range from 360–600 nm. The derivative peak height was measured by peak-zero method at 433 nm. The peak height was plotted against the amount for cobalt to obtain the calibration curve.

The calibration equations were calculated as $A = 0.5417C + 0.0001$ for zero order and $A = 0.2708C + 0.0005$ for the first order derivative data by fitting experimental data. The amount of cobalt present in the alloy sample was determined by the zero order first order derivative method and compared with the certified values.

Results and discussion

The absorption spectra of the reagent and the complex were recorded in wavelength region 360–600 nm at pH 5.5 (Fig. 1). The complex shows absorption maximum at 405 nm where reagent has a negligible absorbance. Hence analytical studies were made at 405 nm against reagent blank. The study of the effect of pH on the colour intensity of the reaction mixture showed that maximum colour was obtained in the pH range 5.0–6.0. Thus, analytical studies were carried out at pH 5.5. A 10-fold molar excess of 2,4-DHBINH was necessary for maximum colour development.

Fig. 1. Absorption spectra of (a) 2,4-DHBINH vs buffer blank and (b) Co^{II} -2,4-DHBINH system vs reagent blank : $\text{Co}^{\text{II}} = 1.2 \times 10^{-5} M$, 2,4-DHBINH = $1.2 \times 10^{-4} M$, pH = 5.5.

The brown colour of Co^{II} -2,4-DHBINH complex was stable in 25% aqueous DMF (v/v). The absorbance of the solution was measured at different time intervals to ascertain the stability of the coloured complex which remained constant for more than 72 h. Beer's law was obeyed in the range of 0.062–1.50 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$. The optimum concentration range was evaluated from Ringbom's plot as 0.090–1.20 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$. The molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity was obtained as $3.20 \pm 0.03 \times 10^4 \text{ L mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and 0.0074 $\mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2$ respectively. The standard deviation for ten determinations of 0.7 μg of cobalt(II) was ± 0.0026 . The correlation coefficient (γ) for the experimental data was calculated as 0.9998.

Effect of foreign ions : The effect of various cations and anions on the determination of Co^{II} under optimal conditions developed was studied to find out the tolerance limits of these ions in the present method. The results are presented in Table 1. Large amounts of commonly associated cations and anions do not interfere in the present method.

In the presence of 600 μg of thiourea, Cu^{II} was tolerable up to 10-fold excess. Th^{IV} and Ni^{II} can be masked up to 9-fold and 10-fold excess respectively by adding 500 μg of citrate.

The composition of the complex was determined using Job's method as 1 : 1 and confirmed by mole-ratio method. The stability constant of the complex was calculated from Job's method and was obtained as 3.3×10^5 .

Determination of cobalt(II) by first-order derivative spectrophotometry : In the zero-order spectrophotometric determination of cobalt with 2,4-DHBINH, the commonly associated metal ions such as Cu^{II} , Th^{IV} , Ni^{II} , Fe^{III} interferes and were masked by using masking agents. The first derivative spectrophotometric method allows selective determination of Co^{II} in presence of these interfering ions without using masking agents.

The first derivative spectra of the Co^{II} -2,4-DHBINH complex with different concentrations of Co^{II} are shown in Fig. 2. The peak zero (h) method was followed for peak height measurements and preparation of calibration plot. The maximum peak amplitude was observed at 433 nm where many foreign ions do not interfere. Hence Co^{II} is determined by measuring the peak zero amplitude at 433 nm. Beer's law was obeyed in the range 0.05–1.8 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$.

Other statistical data derived for the present method were as follows. The standard deviation of the method for ten determinations of 0.096 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$ of Co^{II} was 0.0015. The slope, intercept and the correlation coefficient (γ) of

Fig. 2. First derivative spectra of Co^{II}-2,4-DHBINH vs reagent blank : Co^{II} (μg/ml) (1) 0.295, (2) 0.589, (3) 0.884, (4) 1.178.

the calibration equation for the experimental data were found to be 0.2708, 0.0005 and 1.000 respectively.

The effect of various cations and anions on the derivative amplitude was studied. It was noticed that all the ions that do not interfere in the zero order determination of Co^{II} (Table 1) did not interfere in the first derivative method also. Further, their tolerance limits were in general higher than those of the zero order determination. However, like in zero order method the metal ions Cu^{II}, Fe^{II}, Ni^{II} and V^V interfere in the first derivative spectrophotometric method also.

Application : The proposed method was employed for the determination of Co^{II} in Eligiloy M-1712. The amount of cobalt present in alloy sample was determined by the following procedure.

A known aliquot of the sample solution is taken in a 10 ml volumetric flask containing 5 ml of buffer solution of pH 5.5, 0.5 ml of 0.5 M citrate solution (to mask iron and nickel), 2.5 ml of DMF and 0.5 ml of (5 × 10⁻³ M) reagent solution. The contents of the flask are diluted to 10 ml. The contents, if necessary, are filtered and the absorbance of the filtrate is measured at 405 nm against the reagent blank and the amount of cobalt is calculated from the predetermined calibration plot. The derivative amplitude of the solution is measured at 433 nm. The percentage of Co^{II} found is 39.20 in alloy steel when the certified alloy contains 40.00 only along with other metals.

Conclusions : The first derivative spectrophotometric method was found to be more sensitive than the zero order method for the determination of cobalt(II).

Table 1. Tolerance limits of diverse ions in the determination of cobalt(II)

pH = 5.5, amount of Co^{II} = 0.59 μg/ml

Ion	Tolerance limit (μg/ml)	Ion	Tolerance limit (μg/ml)
Sulphate	4800	Sr ^{II}	292
Chloride	3500	Ba ^{II}	275
Nitrate	3100	Mg ^{II}	240
Fluoride	1900	Ca ^{II}	100
Ascorbate	1760	Fe ^{III}	40 ^a , 30 ^b
Tartrate	1500	Pb ^{II}	40
Iodide	1270	Mo ^{IV}	24
Thiosulphate	1250	Ce ^{IV}	14
Phosphate	950	Ti ^{IV}	12
Oxalate	880	Mn ^{II}	11
Thiourea	760	W ^{VI}	9
Bromate	512	Cu ^{II}	6.3 ^c
Citrate	496	Au ^{III}	6.0
EDTA	Interferes	Zr ^{IV}	6.0
		Th ^{IV}	5.9 ^b
		Ni ^{II}	5.3 ^b
		Cr ^{III}	5.2
		Ag ^I	5.0
		U ^{VI}	2.0
		Zn ^{II}	1.2
		Al ^{III}	Interferes
		V ^V	Interferes

In presence of : ^a500 μg/ml of phosphate, ^b500 μg/ml of citrate, ^c600 μg/ml of thourea.

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